

EBFMC25-OP-03 · Adverse Childhood Experiences Are Associated with Depression and Insomnia in Older Adults

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are potentially traumatic events that occur up to the age of 18 years, and include physical, psychological, sexual abuse and neglect (Felitti et al., 1998; Gilbert et al., 2024). Such trauma often results in chronic stress which are linked to negative health outcomes across the lifespan (Dube et al., 2003). The aim of this study is to reveal the impact of ACE in older age.

Materials and Methods: This was as a cross-sectional study. Data were collected from patients attending one outpatient geriatric clinic. Socio-demographic information on the patients age, gender, marital status, living status, and education level was collected. Subsequently, a comprehensive geriatric assessment (CGA) and ACE scale were conducted. The ACE scale consisted of 10 questions that were categorised as psychological, physical, and sexual sexual abuse, as well as neglect. The relationship between detailed CGA parameters and ACE were analysed.

Results: 319 (the mean age of 76.6 ± 7.2 years, and 76.1% female) older patients were included. The prevalence of ACE was 41.4 %, with psychological ACE being the most common type of ACE. Female gender, number of medications, the presence of insomnia, depression and dysphagia were higher in older patients who experienced at least one ACE than those without ACE ($p < 0.05$). The association between insomnia (OR 1.86, 95% CI 1.15-3.01; $p < 0.05$) and depression (OR 1.71, 95% CI 1.04-2.82; $p < 0.05$) with ACE persisted in multivariate analyses.

Conclusions: ACE was detected in approximately one in every two older adults and was 1.8 times more likely to be associated with insomnia and 1.7 times more likely to be associated with depression. Therefore, when evaluating an older patient experiencing insomnia and depression, ACE should also be evaluated, or insomnia and depression should also be questioned in an older patient experiencing ACE (Daines et al., 2021; Huffman et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2022).

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Adverse childhood experiences, older adults, insomnia, depression, geriatric assessment

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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